

Privacy Concerns of AI in Healthcare

The healthcare industry has recently experienced a rise of artificial intelligence (AI) for medical purposes in the United States. AI requires a quantity of data to provide adequate treatment for patients, which leaves a large pool of patients' personal information vulnerable. With AI comes risks for patients concerning the privacy of their data. Furthermore, when data is compromised, it develops a lack of trust between patients and the healthcare industry. Personal information is compromised by electronic theft, such as hacking and cyberattacks, or by the unauthorized release of information. As these occurrences become prevalent, patients are less likely to want to disclose their personal information in fear that it might be stolen or exposed. Trust is important in the healthcare industry because it promotes "honest communication between the patient and physician, which is essential for quality care," and information security protects people from being prejudiced, humiliated, or financially harmed from reporting their health condition (Miller, 2021, para. 6). Although government agencies claim that healthcare data is protected through de-identification under the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA), privacy concerns could potentially pose challenges with the use of AI in healthcare because sensitive patient data is at risk of being breached and misused.

Government agencies believe that de-identification will secure patient health information, yet companies can still re-identify this data without permission from patients. According to the U.S. Department of Health and Human Services (n.d.) article on the HIPAA, "de-identification, by which identifiers are removed from the health information mitigates privacy risks to individuals and thereby supports the secondary use of data" for numerous endeavors (para. 8). Despite the U.S. government claiming that the HIPAA and de-identification protect patients, loopholes in the system allow for the exploitation of patient information without them knowing.

Unfortunately, due to de-identification, patients do not have the chance to consent on how companies utilize their data, allowing companies unrestricted control over the data. Whether companies sell it or use it for research, patients are oblivious to where their information is going. Not only this, but the laws governing the privacy of the data are outdated. Since the last update of the HIPAA in 2013, there has been a great deal of new technology, including AI, that can not be adapted to this law. In a peer-reviewed article by Rothstein (2010) about the reliability of de-identification, he found that although there are a variety of methods that “deidentify health records,” there is still the possibility “to reidentify them in a surprisingly large number of cases by using computerized network databases” that contain “voter registration records, hospital discharge records, commercially available databases, and other sources” (para. 23). Merely removing certain identifiers is insufficient as there are many more identifiers in the data associated with a particular patient. The ability of AI to recognize individuals has only improved, whether it is by facial ID or genetic information. De-identification does not ensure the total anonymity of a patient because data can be re-identified. Though government laws like the HIPAA allow for the utilization of de-identified data in the healthcare industry, there are still privacy issues since this type of data does not effectively protect patient identities.

While government agencies claim that de-identified information reduces privacy threats, legal experts warn that patient personal information is at risk of being attacked and released. In the *Savannah Law Review's* article about the cybersecurity of AI for the future, Tschider (2017) contends “AI amplifies existing cybersecurity issues because it necessitates ubiquitous data collection, involves reinforced or codified algorithmic calculation, and automates decision-making” (p. 179). Similarly, research that cites multiple sources by Finlayson et al. (2019) about the flaws that cause attacks on AI supports that hospital infrastructure is out of date,

causing “vulnerabilities present in medical software” to most likely “persist for years due to the difficulty and expense involved with updating hospital infrastructure” (pg. 4). To be effective, AI gathers a vast amount of personal data. Since hospital infrastructure has not yet been adapted to the new technology of AI, the volume of patient data is left increasingly vulnerable to cyberattacks. Cyberattacks have gotten more sophisticated than existing hospital systems, employing new tactics to leverage AI and successfully breach the poor data security barriers in place. Once these cybercriminals obtain access to the data, there are many possibilities of what they do with this valuable information: ranging from identity theft, tax fraud, or merely selling it. Moreover, Price and Cohen (2019), a professor at the University of Michigan Law School and a professor of Law at Harvard University, provide specific examples as to how exposure of patients' data can affect daily life: “one’s long-term-care insurance premium goes up, one experiences employment discrimination, one’s HIV status becomes known to those in one’s social circle, etc.” There is an “emotional distress associated with knowing that private medical information is ‘out there’ and potentially exploited by others” (para. 9). Health information is sensitive to each individual. If it is exposed, problems such as discrimination or bias can arise for patients. For instance, private information about one’s health conditions may be undesirable, so when an individual is exposed, it can take a toll on their daily life. Patient information is in a position where it can be easily breached due to AI, allowing for an abundance of possibilities of what might happen to the data.

Along with the risk of cyberattacks, data privacy experts indicate that there is hardly any transparency regarding how companies are handling the data. In a peer-reviewed article, research about managing the development of AI in healthcare shows that AI companies “may not be sufficiently encouraged to always maintain privacy protection if they can monetize the data” and

even “legal penalties are not high enough” to put an end to these practices (Murdoch, 2021, para. 4). Companies undoubtedly use data to their advantage when given the opportunity, demonstrating that privacy is not a priority for them. It should be noted that there may be fines imposed when data is misused by companies; however, companies make more money from the data than the cost of the fine. Hence, nothing motivates companies to change, not even the law, which means they will continue doing this. Companies using de-identified data for these purposes argue that patient identities are protected, yet, de-identification was proved to be ineffective and outdated. In the most current research for the *Journal of Hospital Management and Health Policy* about how organizations handle data, Winter (2021) found that “because the movement and use of data is not typically transparent to data subjects or regulatory authorities, damages may be hard to detect, and monitoring and enforcing compliance may be difficult” (para. 6). Companies use data in ways that they do not reveal to the public to achieve their objectives. Undoubtedly, this dishonesty damages the relationship between patients and the healthcare industry. Eventually, this will lead individuals to seek medical care from other sources, not through the public healthcare system. What companies do with patient information is crucial due to the consequences of mistrust and the possibility of cyberattacks if they can not handle data appropriately.

Overall, the privacy risks associated with AI in healthcare brings concerns over patient information and how companies are utilizing data. While there are government documents, such as the HIPAA, that claim the use of de-identified data is safe and acceptable, the methods of data de-identification are insufficient. Cyberattacks in the healthcare industry will only increase when introducing AI because of various vulnerabilities in the systems. In addition, the lack of transparency in how companies handle data raises concerns. Today, privacy in the age of AI is a

pressing issue; thus, protective measures and rules for protecting healthcare data must be updated accordingly.

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